

RAMONES

Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems

Deliverable

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no2**

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Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities no2

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Disclaimer

RAMONES is a European Innovation Council (EIC) FET Proactive project in the Environmental Intelligence Scope B, related to radically novel approaches to resilient, reliable and environmentally responsible in-situ monitoring, funded by the European Union under Horizon 2020 FET proactive programme, via grant agreement No. 101017808.

RAMONES project's main objective is to close the current marine radioactivity gap in sampling needs and foster new interdisciplinary research in ocean ecosystems. RAMONES will invest a significant effort to provide tools to enable long-term data acquisition missions, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, and propose new AI and Robotics-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. These goals will be achieved by combining state-of-the-art (SoA) methodologies and equipment from various disciplines in a well-balanced synergy. It will also design new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. RAMONES will additionally contribute to shaping a blueprint on Environmental Intelligence in the EU and worldwide.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
E&A	Electronics & Automation
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EIC	European Innovation Council
EMRA	EU-funded Marine Robotics and Applications
EU	European Union
EUMR	EU Merge Control
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
OTF	Outreach Task Force
RSS	Really Simple Syndication service
SoA	State of the Art
WP	Work Package

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Abstract

RAMONES is an ambitious, high-risk project which aims to prove that innovative combination and advancement of recent developments in detector technology and sensor materials, low-power-autonomous robotic systems, and process-modeling theories, have the potential to overcome contemporary limitations and open the window to high temporal and spatial resolution underwater radioactivity measurements, in situ and in near real time, forming a game changer in deep-water environmental monitoring. RAMONES proposes a new generation of submarine radiation-sensing instruments, assisted by State of the Art (SoA) robotic and artificial intelligence (AI) solutions towards understanding radiation related risks near and far from coastal areas, while providing data for the international community towards shaping new policies and governance guidelines for environmental sustainability, economic growth and human health. RAMONES will provide tools for long-term, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, propose new AI-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. All these can be achieved by combining SoA equipment from various disciplines in well-balanced synergy and designing new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. Additionally, one of the main goals is to introduce novel ways of monitoring and response channels to inform key socio-political stakeholders at regular intervals from medium (daily, weekly) to low (monthly to inter-annually) frequencies.

This document is a dissemination, and communication activities report, describing the yearly activities and achievements concerning the promotion of the project together with the results and feedback obtained by our audience / counterparts in the scope of WP5 of the RAMONES project.

The document presents based on the classification listed in the Table 1 of Deliverable 5.9.

- The report of activities carried out during the second-year period (M13-M24), considering the digital channels, the material and templates dealing mainly with Communication activities, the articles and publications, the scientific events and activities organized and participated, and the Environmental-, Radioactivity-, and Robotics-domain oriented activities as main Citizen Awareness and Dissemination activities
- The established KPIs and outreach and dissemination activities

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The outreach and liaison activities, targeting the dissemination of the project objectives and results to wider audiences and the general public (see also nomenclature in Table 1 in the Del 5.9), are separated from the present Deliverable and presented in detail in the Deliverable 5.16 (“Report on Outreach and Liaison Activities no1”, M24).

1. WP5 / Dissemination & Communication Tasks

1.1 WP Objectives related to Dissemination and Communication

The objectives of WP5 which are relevant to the Citizen Awareness, Dissemination and Communication Activities are : (i) to establish a visual and textually recognizable impression of the project and its work; (ii) to maximize the impactful visibility of project's work and achievements; (iii) to engage stakeholders that can support sustainability of the project via both update and feedback provisioning and can further empower the vision around the scientific domain communities, and (iv) to provide essential information and knowledge on the RAMONES project to 3rd parties activating esp. in H2020 and Environmental Intelligence landscape.

The WP is organized into six (6) tasks, of which the four (4) most relevant to the dissemination and outreach activities are presented below (T5.3-5.6).

2. Communication activities

2.1 Digital channels

2.1.1 RAMONES project website

The design and development of RAMONES' website (<https://ramones-project.eu/>) was presented in the deliverable "D5.23 Website, Social Media" on M1 and its final release with some additions was presented in the document "D5.15 Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach no2".

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Figure 1 - RAMONES website (final release)

Metrics

The project's website is an active page updated on a monthly basis, in the context of news, events, publications, deliverables. The objectives of the website are closely related to the promotion and dissemination of the project's activities and material to an online audience, including stakeholders, general audience etc. The activity and statistics of the website are illustrated in the figures below.

Website activity - Monthly summary

Figure 2 - Website activity concerning top users and top pageviews per month

In Fig. 2, the monthly project activity between M13 and M24 and users' interaction with the website are presented in a simple dual chart.

Moreover, the following resulting figures reflect a continuous and transversal work carried out by all partners during the second year of the project.

the visitors per country and the number of sessions per country, respectively.

The statistical information of the website activity is periodically analyzed by means of the Google Analytics tool. The information concerning the location of the visitors, the visitors per country, website sessions per country, as well as the new users and pageviews per month are presented in the following figures. The reports that run on the website clearly show that the RAMONES project has caught the attention of visitors from many different countries around the world.

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Audience Overview

Figure 3 - Overview of the users per month and more statistics of the website

Figure 4 - Overview of the pageviews per month and more statistics of the website

Figure 5 - Main visitors to RAMONES website per country

The following graphs show an overview of the distribution of the website visitors and sessions per country.

Figure 6 - Distribution of website visitors per country

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Figure 7 - Distribution of website sessions per country (top-10)

Finally, a cumulative curve of the new users per month shows that new users are constantly increasing.

Figure 8 - New users per month cumulative curve

2.1.2 Social media

The five (5) social media channels (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube) of the RAMONES project are all linked with the website and are aligned to the project identity principles. Similar to the website, the social networks' activity is periodically monitored, in order for the partners to be informed of the effectiveness of each one of these platforms.

Tracking and metrics

RAMONES activity in social networks is continuous, both in the generation of content and in the interaction with followers and stakeholders. Every event attended and scientific news added in the project's blog is also posted in the social media channels on a monthly basis. As a result, a high impact has been achieved and the activity appeals to a wide audience, as illustrated in the following figures.

On Facebook, an average of 3 posts per month were published, during a 12-month period in the second year of the project (M13-M24) with overall good impression and interaction indices. The facebook page reach during the second year of the project was increased (109,3%) reaching 4.946 number of persons.

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Figure 9 - Summary of Facebook activity of the second year of the project (M13-M24)

Statistics about the age and gender of the followers on Facebook draw interesting inferences from the audience originating mostly from European countries (Greece, France, U.K., Portugal, Germany, Italy, Holland, Sweden, Switzerland) and the U.S.A. The Total number of followers is 490 and total likes 465.

Figure 10 - An estimation of the Facebook followers per gender

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The metrics also concern the views of the Facebook page during the second year of the project.

Figure 11 - Views of our Facebook page during the second year of the project

A total of 44 posts have been published on our Instagram account since the beginning of the project that promotes our scope, daily activities, goals and achievements. The Instagram community is expanding reaching a total of 77 followers. Finally, the Instagram impressions increased the second year compared to the first year of the project by 104,5%, with a total of 730 impressions.

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Figure 12 - Per month Instagram impression of the second year of the project (M13-M24)

Figure 13 - Total views of our Instagram page per month

On Twitter, 65 tweets have been published on a monthly average during M12-M24, highly exceeding the project objectives and many retweets respectively. The page has 81 active followers and several other users that react to our tweets.

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Following is the monthly Twitter analytics for the period M13-M24.

Your Tweets earned **889 impressions** over this **31 day** period

Your Tweets earned **1.3K impressions** over this **28 day** period

Your Tweets earned **315 impressions** over this **31 day** period

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Your Tweets earned **1.4K impressions** over this **30 day** period

Your Tweets earned **434 impressions** over this **31 day** period

Your Tweets earned **1.2K impressions** over this **30 day** period

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Your Tweets earned **972 impressions** over this **31 day** period

Your Tweets earned **72 impressions** over this **31 day** period

Your Tweets earned **394 impressions** over this **30 day** period

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Your Tweets earned **237 impressions** over this **31 day** period

Your Tweets earned **916 impressions** over this **30 day** period

Your Tweets earned **240 impressions** over this **31 day** period

Figure 14 - Monthly Twitter analytics for the @ramones_eu account (01.01.2022-31.12.2022)

Between M12 and M24, 8.367 new tweet impressions have been registered, reaching a total of 26.661 impressions overall, thus reaching 265% of the initially targeted 10.000 social media impressions for the full lifecycle of the project. The figure below shows the monthly evolution.

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M12-M24 total impressions

Figure 15 - RAMONES monthly tweet impressions

M12-M24 total tweets

Figure 16 - RAMONES monthly tweets

The analysis of the number of impressions to RAMONES twitter profile is an indication of how the project triggers interest, as well as the extent to which it is becoming known. The impact is closely linked to relevant events (such as the International Fair of Thessaloniki, participation in events and congresses, other fairs and exhibitions).

Due to the global coronavirus pandemic, all face-to-face activities have been severely restricted. To overcome this limitation, all the digital channels of the project have been strengthened and online activity has been strongly reinforced.

All the previous figures show the results obtained. The following figure illustrates the impact obtained compared to what was planned at the beginning of the project under normal conditions.

On LinkedIn, a total of 17 new posts (total 30) were published during the (M13-M24) period receiving 287 new likes (total 350). The total views have been raised by 3601 new impressions and the followers until today are 98 (+29 gain). The following is a sample of 3 posts metrics of the LinkedIn platform.

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Figure 17 - Sample of a LinkedIn post metrics

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On YouTube, 3 video posts are available to the public which have attracted an aggregate of 52 views. A total of 10 subscribers (+4 in M13-M24) have been recorded. The following pictures show the metrics of YouTube, such as total views and total impressions.

Figure 18 - Total views

Figure 19 - Total impressions

Finally, in the second year of the project again Twitter and Facebook are the main social media platforms that gather the most followers and impressions. LinkedIn, Instagram and YouTube are less popular than the other platforms, but still attract public attention.

2.1.3 Mailing & Newsletter activities

The RAMONES mailing list is a collection of email addresses of people that have subscribed to our newsletter through the project website. More people have subscribed to our newsletter in order to get project updates relative to radioactivity monitoring, environmental intelligence and other scientific fields but also to stay informed regarding our dissemination activities.

Newsletters

Two newsletters have been published in the second year of the project (at M18 and M24), complying with the committed biannual rate. The newsletters comprise four articles each, which have been published in the RAMONES blog and received recognition or their content was considered more suitable for the general public. The topics have been studied with the participation of all partners, presenting achievements, news, participation in events, general and scientific information and much more, considering the needs of the project stage.

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General information about the project and the members was also provided.

The following are indicative images that illustrate parts of the released 3rd and 4th newsletters. At the point of authoring this report, the number of subscribers has reached 477.

Holiday wishes

Happy and Joyful Holidays and a prosperous New Year 2023!

[Read more →](#)

First RAMONES trials performed with the IST Glider

The RAMONES consortium is happy to announce that the first trials with one of the Autonomous Underwater Gliders took place in Portugal last 21st October in a test tank owned by EMEPC (Portuguese Task Group for the Extension of the Continental Shelf). The major goal of...

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FRAGRANCE Workshop organized by the NKUA

RAMONES organized a dedicated Workshop at 24 June, 2022 in hybrid format to consolidate and extend the existing scientific collaboration between the Departments of Physics at the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens and Université Clermont Auvergne. Both academic institutions are partners in RAMONES working on common and parallel research tasks to achieve the innovative goals and meet the ultimate objects of the EU H2020-funded project.

For more information visit the site of the workshop:

<https://sites.google.com/view/fragrance-workshop/home>

Read more →

RAMONES and NODSSUM: a collaboration for the oceans

A project to investigate the fate of radioactive waste dumped in the North-East Atlantic abyssal plains is the focus of a CNRS Journal article (<https://lejournal.cnrs.fr/articles/atlantique-sur-la-piste-des-futs-radioactifs>).

NODSSUM plans to deploy a new deep-sea AUV developed by IFREMER (France), Ulyx, and that will be part of the French Oceanographic Fleet, and a remotely operated vehicle VICTOR, during 2 cruises that are programmable from 2023. The first cruise will map the areas that concentrated ~50% of the radioactive waste dump, with likely up to 200.000 drums or more from the 40's to the 80's. Both sonar and optical surveys will provide the distribution and status of barrels, and carry out some preliminary sampling of seawater, sediment, and biota away from the barrels.

Read more →

RAMONES webinar: “Hunting Radioactivity in the Depths of the Ocean”

Get ready to join our webinar! RAMONES project is pleased to invite you to attend a webinar by our Coordinator, Theo J. Mertzimekis, who will speak about “Hunting Radioactivity in the Depths of the Ocean”.

Mark your calendar: **Tue 28.06.2022 at 11’00 CET.**

and register here to receive a webcast link:

<https://tinyurl.com/RAMONESwebinar>

[Read more →](#)

Find us online

Be the first to receive valuable insights and scientific nuggets from RAMONES! We are always interested in your views. Reply to this email if you have any queries about the content of this newsletter, or anything else.

RAMONES receives funding from European Union under Horizon 2020 FET Proactive Programme via grant agreement No. 101017808

Figure 20 - RAMONES 3rd and 4th Newsletter (extract)

3. Dissemination activities

3.1 Publishing activities (Articles and publications)

Articles of general interest may be distributed over the press, other media sites or the web site of the project. Articles and publication production includes general purpose articles, press and media content, and scientific publications. The primary language is English, in order to reach the widest potential audience. However, the languages spoken in the project have been used according to the specific scope, published in other languages too. The website is the natural place to host all the work generated.

3.1.1 Articles of general and scientific purpose

A public-interest article related to the RAMONES project was published on-line in the Hub website of NKUA in February 2022, under the title 'The first radiological maps of the NKUA University campus of Zografou, in greek. The article points out the reassuring outcomes of the research concerning radioactivity measurements conducted in the University campus. The outcomes were also published in the Nuclear Energy and Technology Journal.

<https://hub.uoa.gr/the-first-radiological-maps-of-the-campus-of-zografou/>

The articles of scientific interest are 6 journal papers (Peer reviewed) and 2 conference papers (Peer reviewed):

Journal Papers (Peer reviewed)

1. P. Nomikou, P. N. Polymenakou, A. L. Rizzo, S. Petersen, M. Hannington, S. P. Kiliias, D.Papanikolaou, J. Escartin, K. Karantzalos, Th. J. Mertzimekis, V. Antoniou, M. Krokos, L. Grammatikopoulos, F. Italiano, C. G. Caruso, G. Lazzaro, M. Longo, S. S. Scappuzzo, W. D'Alessandro, F. Grassa, K. Bejelou, D. Lampridou, A. Katsigera & A. Dura, '*SANTORY: SANTORini's Seafloor Volcanic Observatory*', *Front. Mar. Sci.*, Mar. 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.796376>
2. P. Batista, D. Cabecinhas, L. Sebastião, A.Pascoal, T. Mertzimekis, K. Kebkal, A. Mallios, K. Karantzalos, K. Nikolopoulos, J. Escartín, L. Maigne, '*The EU project RAMONES – continuous, long-term autonomous monitoring of underwater radioactivity*', *7as Jornadas de Engenharia Hidrográfica / 2as Jornadas Luso-Espanholas de Hidrografia*, Lisbon, Portugal, Hydrographic Institute, Jun. 2022
3. N. Hung, F. Rego, J. Quintas, J. Cruz, M. Jacinto, D. Souto, A. Potes, L. Sebastião, A. Pascoal, '*A review of path following control strategies for autonomous robotic vehicles*:'

- theory, simulations, and experiments*', Journal of Field Robotics, April 2022, doi: 10.1002/rob.22142
4. P. Maurya, H. Morishita, A. Pascoal & A. P. Aguiar, '*A path following controller for marine vehicles using a two scale inner-outer loop approach*', Sensors 2022, 22(11), 4293, Special Issue on Motion Optimization and Control of Single and Multiple Autonomous Aerial, Land, and Marine Robots, Jun. 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22114293>
 5. C. Kielas-Jensen, V. Cichella, T. Berry, I. Kaminer, C. Walton, A. Pascoal, '*A Bernstein polynomial-based method for solving optimal trajectory generation problems*', Sensors 2022, 22(5), 1869, Special Issue on Motion Optimization and Control of Single and Multiple Autonomous Aerial, Land, and Marine Robots, Feb. 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22051869>

Conference Papers (peer reviewed)

6. S. Venkataramanan, B. Psomas, Y. Avrithis, E. Kijak, L. Amsaleg, K. Karantzas, '*It Takes Two to Tango: Mixup for Deep Metric Learning*', International Conference on Learning Representations, California, Apr. 25-29, 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2106.04990>
7. I. Kakogeorgiou, S. Gidaris, B. Psomas, Y. Avrithis, A. Bursuc, K. Karantzas, N. Komodakis, '*What to Hide from Your Students: Attention-Guided Masked Image Modeling*', in: Avidan, S., Brostow, G., Cissé, M., Farinella, G.M., Hassner, T. (eds) Computer Vision – ECCV 2022. European Conference on Computer Vision (ECCV) 2022. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 13690, pp 300–318. Springer, Cham, , Nov. 2022,, doi: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-20056-4_18

3.2 Invited talks and lectures

The invited lectures listed below include topics that were inspired by and cover many of the topics addressed in the scope of the RAMONES project:

1. K. Nikolopoulos, Arab Open University, Kuwait, Jun. 29, 2022
2. K. Nikolopoulos, Gulf University of Science and Technology, Kuwait, Jun. 30, 2022.

3.3 Meetings

The RAMONES team held many meetings, mainly by teleconference. Several meetings with relevant stakeholders and policy makers (e.g. with board members of the Greek Atomic Energy Commission or CNRS Executive Officers), presenting RAMONES and discussing innovation, business and the challenges of new technology and services to keep up-to-date and enrich the knowledge about the scope of the project, being the RAMONES digital channels, a fruitful point of contact.

3.4 Scientific events

The RAMONES team held many meetings, mainly by teleconference. Several meetings with relevant stakeholders

Table 1 - Scientific Workshops and conferences (co)organised or participated by RAMONES

Event Name	Type of event	RAMONES role	Place & Date
Black Sea CONNECT Innovation Workshop	Workshop	invited presentation	Online, 2/2/2022
7as Jornadas de Engenharia Hidrográfica / 2as Jornadas Luso-Espanholas de Hidrografia	Conference	participation	21-23/6/2022
FRAGRANCE Workshop FRAGRANCE	Workshop	(co)organization	24/6/2022
5th International Conference on Radioecology & Environmental Radioactivity	Conference	participation	4-9/9/2022
2022 LARSyS Annual Meeting	Annual meeting	participation	14-15/7/2022

Figure 21 - A picture from the FRAGRANCE Workshop

4. Summary

As a conclusion, the following table summarizes the indicators of success of the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities. The details are presented in the Report of Activities section above.

1. KPI's concerning user (supply and demand) attraction up to the 24th month of the project (completion of the second year):

Table 2 - KPIs concerning user (supply and demand) attraction

Range	Type of dissemination and communication activities	Target	Contributed values	Accomplished
Ecosystem	Workshops / conferences (co)organized.	6	6	100%
Ecosystem	Workshops supported by presenters and panelists on project specific topics.	14	11	78%

2. KPIs concerning scientific dissemination:

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Table 3 - KPIs concerning scientific dissemination

Range	Type of dissemination and communication activities	Target	Contributed values	Accomplished
Wide range	Average social media posts per month	2	4	200%
Wide range	General public articles languages supported	4	2	50%
Ecosystem	Peer reviewed scientific publications	10	16	160%
Ecosystem	Other scientific publications and artifacts	12	15	125%
Ecosystem	References and acknowledgements	50	29	58%
Ecosystem	Whitepapers (as per work plan)	3	0	0
Ecosystem	Multimedia & training material published	8	3	38%
Ecosystem	Percentage of Open Access publications	>70%	85%	121%
Wide range	Fairs and exhibitions participated	3	4	133%
Wide range	Commercial exploitation events participation	5	2	40%

3. KPIs concerning social dissemination:

Table 4 - KPIs concerning social dissemination

Range	Type of dissemination and communication activities	Target	Contributed values	Accomplished
Wide range	Websites launched (workplan)	1	1	100%
Wide range	Website content updating (average)	monthly	monthly	100%
Ecosystem	Templates for dissemination activities and other material	2	2	100%
Ecosystem	Hardcopy/tangible material forms	3	8	266%

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Wide range	Social media dissemination channels	4	5	125%
Wide range	Social media impressions (social media channels total)	10000	20902	209%
Wide range	Social media followers (total across media)	1200	676	56%
Wide range	Average technical blog posts per year	2	2	100%
Wide range	Average general public blog posts per year	6	5	83%
Wide range	General public articles on printed or online media	8	5	62%
Wide range	Newsletters issued (biannual)	8	4	50%

4. KPIs concerning strengthen impact via joint efforts:

Table 5 - KPIs concerning strengthening impact via joint efforts

Range	Type of dissemination and communication activities	Target	Contributed values	Accomplished
Ecosystem	Relevant H2020 Projects & other projects liaised with RAMONES	6	7	116%
Ecosystem	MoUs signed with 3rd parties.	5	2	40%
Ecosystem	Datathons/hackathons organized by the project	2	0	0
Ecosystem	3rd party datathons/hackathons supported by project	2	0	0
Ecosystem	Datathons/hackathons participants	200	0	0
Ecosystem	Individuals directly addressed via scientific, academic communication, innovation stimulation, training and engagement activities	1800	15136	840%